

Transformational Leadership: A Systematic Literature Review for Future Research Agenda

Udin Udin

Universitas Muhammadiyah Yogyakarta, Indonesia
E-mail: udin_labuan@yahoo.com

Abstract: Leadership is one of the subjects often discussed in corporate environments and has been researched in relation to several performance results among employees. Transformational leadership is a style of leadership described by the partnerships between leaders and followers and the outcomes they accomplish together to fulfill organizational objectives. This study provides an analysis of the philosophy of transformational leadership, as well as practical advice for self-reflection and enhancement of leadership behaviors that facilitate successful organizational transformation. A few research have tested the theoretical premise that the positive effects of transformational leadership on people, groups, and organizations are related to the change of followers in real and permanent ways. This study concludes that transformation leadership encompasses mostly four behaviors: idealized influence, intellectual stimulation, inspirational motivation, and individual consideration.

Keywords: Transformational leadership, literature review, future research agenda

I. Introduction

Throughout today's dynamic business environment, leaders who empower followers to achieve strongly and enthusiastically change are greatly appreciated by organizations. Transformational leadership is obsessed with how members accomplish such attainments (B. J. Avolio & Gardner, 2005). Transformation leadership theory has attracted significant academic interest since its creation more than 40 years ago and appears to be one of the leadership paradigms most widely investigated (Crede, Jong, & Harms, 2019; Dinh et al., 2014; Kammerhoff, Lauenstein, & Schütz, 2019; Northouse, 2016).

The theory of transformational leadership becomes a pillar of leadership study (Siangchokyoo, Klinger, & Campion, 2019). The idea that leaders turn followers in circumstances leading to excellent organizational success and offer a persuasive empirical groundwork for both research and practice. Transformational leaders gain a perfect visualization of what the current and future course of action of the business is going across competitive markets (Bernard M Bass & Avolio, 1995). Leaders establish an ambitious vision, have a powerful confidence in that vision, express it explicitly and convey it to the workers so that the latter can trust in and be enthusiastic about the visions of leaders (Zhu, Chew, & Spangler, 2005).

Downton (1973) was thought to be the principal person to use the terms transformational leadership, and Burns (1978) was the original person to distinguish leadership styles based on the motivation of followers. Burns (1978) described transformational leadership as a method of empowering followers to reflect on their ideals and imagine a clear future for them. Forty years after Burns (1978) came up with the thought of the transforming leader, his theories was strengthened by the research of Bass and associates who assisted explain (a) the activities that leaders participate in to facilitate the transition of followers; (b) the forms in which leaders turn followers; and (c) the matrix of results affected by leader-follower experiences. (Bruce J Avolio & Bass, 1988; Bruce J. Avolio & Bass, 1995; Bernard M Bass & Riggio, 2006).

The theory of transformational leadership is based on the postulation that followers change as a consequence of their collaboration with this kind of leader. Burns (1978) explains transforming attributes as requiring "real change" in terms of (a) the extent of change: the behaviors and beliefs of adherents need to be changed to a "significant degree"; and (b) the durability of change: change should be fairly lasting rather than fleeting.

The theory of transformational leadership was developed to understand the difference in the effectiveness of leadership (Jackson, 2020). Transformational leadership often reflects on how the qualities of a leader affect the beliefs, desires, principles, and ambitions of followers so that they prioritize organizational achievement above self-interest. Few analyses have tested the theoretical presumption that the positive effects of transformational leadership on the person, community, and organization are attributable to the transformation of followers in real and lasting ways. Thousands of empirical research paper endorse linkages between transformational leaders and employee, team, and organizational results, generating it difficult to ignore this construct's significance (Camps & Rodríguez, 2011; Rao & Abdul, 2015; Siangchokyoo et al., 2019). Based on the hypothetical and empirical proof, this study, therefore, aims to scrutinize the variable of transformational leadership in the way of systematic literature review for future research agenda.

II. Methods

This study released an exhaustive online search for published studies on transformational leadership. For the online search, this study explored electronic databases such as Science Direct, Emerald Insight, and Google Scholar using combinations of the following keywords: *transformational leadership and authentic leadership*. As a result, a total of 31 primary studies with 22 articles published, met the criteria for inclusion, and were included in the analysis.

Table 1 Reviewed Papers of Transformational Leadership

No.	Author	Country	Sample size	Measures/ dimensions of leadership
1	Luyten and Bazo (2019)	Mozambique	518	Establishing vision and goals, establishing structure, promoting culture, performance expectation, intellectual stimulation, idealized support
2	Elrehail, Emeagwali, Alsaad, and Alzghoul (2018)	Jordan	173	Idealized influence, individualized consideration, intellectual stimulation, inspirational motivation
3	Agi and Nishant (2017)	Gulf countries	13	Commitment to top management, performance monitoring, integration with partners, reward and appraisal systems
4	Blome, Foerstl, and Schleper (2017)	Germany	118	Ethical, obedience to authority
5	Gosling, Jia, Gong, and Brown (2016)	N/A	N/A	Proactive and reactive
6	Mzembe, Lindgreen, Maon, and Vanhamme (2016)	Malawi	37	Organizational contingency, ethical values, advisory
7	Dubey, Gunasekaran, and Ali (2015)	India	306	Vision statement, intellectual stimulation, high-performance expectation, provide the appropriate model
8	Dubey, Singh, and Gupta (2015)	India	187	Long-term vision, establishing policies, stimulating improvement, providing resources
9	Lenssen et al. (2013)	N/A	N/A	Visionary, clear direction, commitment, innovation
10	Lockström and Lei (2013)	China	88	Clear communication, encouraging and involving in teamwork, continuous improvement, autonomy, authority
11	Shahraki and Bahraini (2013)	South Pars	134	Idealized influence, mental persuasion, inspirational motivation, personal consideration
12	Lockström, Schadel, Harrison, Moser, and Malhotra (2010)	China	30	Coaching/cooperative, delegating, situation changing
13	Lambrechts, Taillieu, and Sips (2010)	Belgium	N/A	Pro-activity, including and stimulating, indirectness
14	Wamba and Chatfield (2009)	Australia	N/A	Organizational transformation, communication, change management
15	B. J. Avolio and Bass (2004)	Menlo Park	N/A	Idealized influence (behavior), idealized influence (attributed), intellectual stimulation, inspirational motivation, individual consideration
16	Rafferty and Griffin (2004)	Australia	1398	Articulating vision, inspirational communication, intellectual stimulation, supportive leader, personal recognition
17	Williams, Esper, and Ozment (2002)	N/A	N/A	Visionary, flexibility, consideration and appreciation, dynamic, decision making, long-term collaboration, encouragement
18	Segars, Harkness, and Kettinger (2001)	USA	N/A	Visionary, investigator, coach, innovator, change agent
19	MacKenzie, Podsakoff, and Rich (2001)	USA	477	Core transformational leadership behavior, supportive leader behavior, high-performance expectations, intellectual stimulation
20	McAdam and Brown	UK	N/A	Visionary and coach

	(2001)			
21	Podsakoff, MacKenzie, Moorman, and Fetter (1990)	Midwest	N/A	Recognizing and formulating a vision, presenting an appropriate model, fostering acceptance of group goals, high-performance expectations, giving individualized support, intellectual stimulation
22	B. M. Bass (1985)	New York	N/A	Idealized influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, individualized consideration

III. Results and Discussion

Leadership is relevant in many organizations (Buil, Martínez, & Matute, 2019; Leroy, Segers, van Dierendonck, & den Hartog, 2018) and it puts emphasis on understanding, forecasting, and influencing personal and interpersonal dynamics of how people influence one another towards shared goals (Northouse, 2016). Leadership in the organization is seen as an important tool for environmental management (Babić, Savović, & Domanović, 2014; Crede et al., 2019; Guest & Teplitzky, 2010; Zhou, Zhang, Lyu, & Zhang, 2018).

Transformational leadership involves building an innovative climate among different types of leadership, heartening, stimulating, and encouraging employees to trust with the insight of a leader that directly impacts firm creativity and performance (Boehm, Dwertmann, Bruch, & Shamir, 2015; Ng, 2017). The style of transformational leadership is to help inspire followers through imperative vision, individual support, and empowerment. Based on Table 1, transformation leadership encompasses mostly four behaviors: idealized influence, intellectual stimulation, inspirational motivation, and individual consideration. Zhu et al. (2005) note that transformational leadership is promoting higher levels of inspiration, trust, unity, commitment, and performance. A number of studies showed that the strategically driven dimension of transformational leadership has a beneficial impact on performance, talent management and competitiveness in the workforce (Carton, Murphy, & Clark, 2014; Jia, Liu, Chin, & Hu, 2018; Naderi, Vosta, Ebrahimi, & Jalilvand, 2019; Singh, Giudice, Chierici, & Graziano, 2020).

IV. Conclusion

Transformational leaders have a strong view of the current and future course of action of the company in the face of competitive markets. Transformational leadership has the capacity to deliver out of reach. Transformational leadership generates an ambitious dream, obviously believes in that vision, articulates it, and specifically expresses it to the employees. This study concludes that transformation leadership encompasses mostly four behaviors: idealized influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individual consideration.

References

Agi, M. A., & Nishant, R. (2017). Understanding influential factors on implementing green supply chain management practices: An interpretive structural modelling analysis. *Journal of environmental management*, 188, 351-363.

Avolio, B. J., & Bass, B. M. (1988). Transformational leadership, charisma, and beyond.

Avolio, B. J., & Bass, B. M. (1995). Individual consideration viewed at multiple levels of analysis: A multi-level framework for examining the diffusion of transformational leadership. *The leadership quarterly*, 6(2), 199-218. doi: [https://doi.org/10.1016/1048-9843\(95\)90035-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/1048-9843(95)90035-7)

Avolio, B. J., & Bass, B. M. (2004). *MLQ – Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire*. Menlo Park, CA: Mind Garden, Inc.

Avolio, B. J., & Gardner, W. L. (2005). Authentic leadership development: Getting to the root of positive forms of leadership. *The leadership quarterly*, 16(3), 315-338.

Babić, V. M., Savović, S. D., & Domanović, V. M. (2014). Transformational leadership and post-acquisition performance in transitional economies. *Journal of Organizational Change Management*, 27(6), 856-876. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1108/JOCM-02-2014-0028>

Bass, B. M. (1985). *Leadership and performance beyond expectations*. New York, NY: Free Press.

Bass, B. M., & Avolio, B. J. (1995). *MLQ multifactor leadership questionnaire technical report*. Binghamton University, NY: Center for Leadership Studies.

Bass, B. M., & Riggio, R. E. (2006). *Transformational leadership*. Mahwah, NJ: Erlbaum.

Blome, C., Foerstl, K., & Schleper, M. C. (2017). Antecedents of green supplier championing and greenwashing: An empirical study on leadership and ethical incentives. *Journal of cleaner production*, 152, 339-350.

Boehm, S. A., Dwertmann, D. J. G., Bruch, H., & Shamir, B. (2015). The missing link? Investigating organizational identity strength and transformational leadership climate as mechanisms that connect CEO charisma with firm performance. *The leadership quarterly*, 26(2), 156-171. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.leaqua.2014.07.012>

Buil, I., Martínez, E., & Matute, J. (2019). Transformational leadership and employee performance: The role of identification, engagement and proactive personality. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 77, 64-75. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhm.2018.06.014>

Burns, J. (1978). *Leadership*. New York: Harper & Row.

Camps, J., & Rodríguez, H. (2011). Transformational leadership, learning, and employability. *Personnel Review*, 40(4), 423-442. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1108/00483481111133327>

Transformational Leadership: A Systematic Literature Review for Future Research Agenda

- Carton, A. M., Murphy, C., & Clark, J. R. (2014). A (blurry) vision of the future: How leader rhetoric about ultimate goals influences performance. *Academy of Management Journal*, 57(6), 1544-1570.
- Crede, M., Jong, J., & Harms, P. (2019). The generalizability of transformational leadership across cultures: a meta-analysis. *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, 34(3), 139-155. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1108/JMP-11-2018-0506>
- Dinh, J. E., Lord, R. G., Gardner, W. L., Meuser, J. D., Liden, R. C., & Hu, J. (2014). Leadership theory and research in the new millennium: Current theoretical trends and changing perspectives. *The leadership quarterly*, 25(1), 36-62. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.leaqua.2013.11.005>
- Downton, J. V. (1973). *Rebel leadership: Commitment and charisma in the revolutionary process*: Free Press.
- Dubey, R., Gunasekaran, A., & Ali, S. S. (2015). Exploring the relationship between leadership, operational practices, institutional pressures and environmental performance: A framework for green supply chain. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 160, 120-132.
- Dubey, R., Singh, T., & Gupta, O. K. (2015). Impact of agility, adaptability and alignment on humanitarian logistics performance: Mediating effect of leadership. *Global Business Review*, 16(5), 812-831.
- Elrehail, H., Emeagwali, O. L., Alsaad, A., & Alzghoul, A. (2018). The impact of transformational and authentic leadership on innovation in higher education: the contingent role of knowledge sharing. *Telematics and Informatics*, 35(1), 55-67.
- Gosling, J., Jia, F., Gong, Y., & Brown, S. (2016). The role of supply chain leadership in the learning of sustainable practice: toward an integrated framework. *Journal of cleaner production*, 137, 1458-1469.
- Guest, D. W., & Teplitzky, A. L. (2010). High-performance environmental management systems: Lessons learned from 250 visits at leadership facilities. *Environmental Quality Management*, 20(1), 25-38.
- Jackson, C. J. (2020). Transformational leadership and gravitas: 2000 years of no development? *Personality and Individual Differences*, 156, 109760. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2019.109760>
- Jia, J., Liu, H., Chin, T., & Hu, D. (2018). The continuous mediating effects of GHRM on employees' green passion via transformational leadership and green creativity. *Sustainability*, 10(9), 3237.
- Kammerhoff, J., Lauenstein, O., & Schütz, A. (2019). Leading toward harmony – Different types of conflict mediate how followers' perceptions of transformational leadership are related to job satisfaction and performance. *European Management Journal*, 37(2), 210-221. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.emj.2018.06.003>
- Lambrechts, F., Taillieu, T., & Sips, K. (2010). Learning to work with interdependencies effectively: the case of the HRM forum of the suppliers teams at Volvo Cars Gent. *Supply Chain Management: An International Journal*, 15(2), 95-100.
- Lenssen, G., Painter, M., Ionescu-Somers, A., Pickard, S., Szekely, F., & Strebler, H. (2013). Incremental, radical and game-changing: strategic innovation for sustainability. *Corporate governance*.
- Leroy, H., Segers, J., van Dierendonck, D., & den Hartog, D. (2018). Managing people in organizations: Integrating the study of HRM and leadership. *Human Resource Management Review*, 28(3), 249-257. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hrmr.2018.02.002>
- Lockström, M., & Lei, L. (2013). Antecedents to supplier integration in China: A partial least squares analysis. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 141(1), 295-306.
- Lockström, M., Schadel, J., Harrison, N., Moser, R., & Malhotra, M. K. (2010). Antecedents to supplier integration in the automotive industry: a multiple-case study of foreign subsidiaries in China. *Journal of Operations Management*, 28(3), 240-256.
- Luyten, H., & Bazo, M. (2019). Transformational leadership, professional learning communities, teacher learning and learner centred teaching practices; Evidence on their interrelations in Mozambican primary education. *Studies in educational evaluation*, 60, 14-31.
- MacKenzie, S. B., Podsakoff, P. M., & Rich, G. A. (2001). Transformational and Transactional Leadership and Salesperson Performance. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 29(2), 115-134.
- McAdam, R., & Brown, L. (2001). Strategic alignment and the supply chain for the steel stockholder sector: an exploratory case study analysis. *Supply Chain Management: An International Journal*, 6(2), 83-95.
- Mzembe, A. N., Lindgreen, A., Maon, F., & Vanhamme, J. (2016). Investigating the drivers of corporate social responsibility in the global tea supply chain: A case study of Eastern Produce Limited in Malawi. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 23(3), 165-178.
- Naderi, A., Vosta, L. N., Ebrahimi, A., & Jalilvand, M. R. (2019). The contributions of social entrepreneurship and transformational leadership to performance. *International Journal of Sociology and Social Policy*, 39(9/10), 719-737. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJSSP-06-2019-0124>
- Ng, T. W. H. (2017). Transformational leadership and performance outcomes: Analyses of multiple mediation pathways. *The leadership quarterly*, 28(3), 385-417. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.leaqua.2016.11.008>
- Northouse, P. (2016). *Leadership: Theory and practice (7th ed.)*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Podsakoff, P., MacKenzie, S., Moorman, R., & Fetter, R. (1990). Transformational leadership behaviors and their effects on followers' trust in leader: satisfaction and organizational citizenship behaviors. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 1, 107-142.
- Rafferty, A. E., & Griffin, M. A. (2004). Dimensions of transformational leadership: conceptual and empirical extensions. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 15(3), 329-354.
- Rao, A. S., & Abdul, W. K. (2015). Impact of transformational leadership on team performance: an empirical study in UAE. *Measuring Business Excellence*, 19(4), 30-56. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1108/MBE-07-2014-0022>

Transformational Leadership: A Systematic Literature Review for Future Research Agenda

- Segars, A. H., Harkness, W. J., & Kettinger, W. J. (2001). Process management and supply-chain integration at the Bose Corporation. *Interfaces*, 31(3), 102-114.
- Shahraki, M. R., & Bahraini, Z. (2013). An Examination of the relationship between transformational leadership with Entrepreneurial Orientation in organization (Case Study: Mobin Petrochemical Company - South Pars). *International Journal of Advanced Studies in Humanities and Social Science*, 1(4), 274-289.
- Siangchokyoo, N., Klinger, R. L., & Campion, E. D. (2019). Follower transformation as the linchpin of transformational leadership theory: A systematic review and future research agenda. *The leadership quarterly*, 101341. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.leaqua.2019.101341>
- Singh, S. K., Giudice, M. D., Chierici, R., & Graziano, D. (2020). Green innovation and environmental performance: The role of green transformational leadership and green human resource management. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 150, 119762. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2019.119762>
- Wamba, S. F., & Chatfield, A. T. (2009). A contingency model for creating value from RFID supply chain network projects in logistics and manufacturing environments. *European Journal of Information Systems*, 18(6), 615-636.
- Williams, L. R., Esper, T. L., & Ozment, J. (2002). The electronic supply chain: Its impact on the current and future structure of strategic alliances, partnerships and logistics leadership. *International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management*, 32(8), 703-719.
- Zhou, S., Zhang, D., Lyu, C., & Zhang, H. (2018). Does seeing “mind acts upon mind” affect green psychological climate and green product development performance? The role of matching between green transformational leadership and individual green values. *Sustainability*, 10(9), 3206.
- Zhu, W., Chew, I. K. H., & Spangler, W. D. (2005). CEO transformational leadership and organizational outcomes: The mediating role of human-capital-enhancing human resource management. *The leadership quarterly*, 16(1), 39-52. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.leaqua.2004.06.001>